

Rethinking Dual Learning in Flanders: Towards a More Inclusive and Effective Model

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Summary

1. Dual learning in Flanders has not met expectations, with low uptake and a system that currently favours academically stronger students.
2. Vulnerable learners face barriers due to rigid entry requirements, limited flexibility, and insufficient support in transitioning between tracks.
3. Schools and employers struggle with complex regulations and underfunded coordination, which limits participation and sustainability.
4. The focus on expanding dual learning into theoretically oriented tracks (double finality) has yielded limited results and may not align with labour market realities.
5. To succeed, dual learning requires more flexible pathways and simplified procedures.

1. Introduction

Since its formal launch in 2019, the Flemish dual learning system - where students split their education between school and a workplace - was expected to become a flagship reform bridging education and employment. Inspired by successful international models such as Germany and Switzerland, dual learning was positioned as a means to combat youth unemployment, reduce early school leaving, and better align educational outcomes with labour market needs. However, five years into its implementation,

the system has not lived up to these high expectations.

Participation remains low, particularly in the tracks that were meant to attract a broader range of students, including those in the more academically oriented double finality. In Flanders, dual learning continues to serve only a small segment of the student population. Schools and employers alike struggle with complex administrative demands, underfunded support structures, and a system that appears tailored primarily to students already deemed 'strong' in terms of academic or behavioural profiles.

Meanwhile, early school leaving remains worryingly high - especially among vulnerable students who were originally intended to benefit most from a more practical, workplace-oriented education. The integration of the former part-time vocational education (DBSO) into the new dual learning system has also exposed tensions, particularly as many of these students do not meet the stricter requirements of the dual track.

This policy brief assesses the current shortcomings of dual learning in Flanders, and outlines the adjustments needed to make this system truly inclusive, flexible, and sustainable.

2. The issues

Despite initial optimism, the uptake of dual learning in Flanders has remained limited. In the 2022–2023 school year, only 6.6% of students in the second and third grades of vocational education (BSO) and technical education (TSO) participated in dual learning. When including the older, now-phasing-out tracks of DBSO and Leertijd, total participation in work-based learning reached just 14,000 students - far below the potential suggested by policy ambitions. This modest growth is particularly disappointing given the goal to replace not only DBSO and Leertijd, but also to expand into new student populations.

A major issue is the system's overemphasis on "strong" students. Dual learning was meant to be a broad, high-quality pathway, but it has mainly attracted students with stronger academic backgrounds and fewer support needs. Vulnerable students - those with learning delays, behavioural challenges, or socio-economic disadvantages - often find the system too rigid or demanding. These students, who previously found some support

in the more flexible DBSO, now struggle with the standardised requirements of dual learning. As a result, many fail to transition from the preparatory 'onboarding' phase to a full dual learning track.

A second challenge concerns the system's complexity. Employers must meet strict recognition criteria, provide trained mentors, and navigate cumbersome administrative procedures. For many SMEs, these demands are too high, limiting the availability of suitable work placements. At the same time, schools face coordination difficulties, as they must offer both full-time and dual tracks, often with insufficient resources.

The reform also struggles in the so-called double finality track, where it aimed to attract technically skilled students. Here, uptake is minimal, and the added value of workplace learning is harder to realise due to more theoretical curricula. Employers are also less inclined to invest in students likely to pursue higher education, reducing placement availability.

Moreover, transitioning back to a non-dual track is often difficult for students who fail to secure a work placement within the required 20 days. This rigid structure leaves little room for trial and error and contributes to dropout risks. Indeed, early school leaving remains a critical issue: 13.2% of Flemish students dropped out in 2022, and the rate is much higher among dual learners with a DBSO background.

Lastly, funding issues persist. Schools must often organise duplicate pathways, increasing costs without proportionate support. External guidance, especially for the onboarding phase, lacks sufficient capacity as scale economies are lacking. These structural flaws hinder the broader rollout and success of dual learning.

3. Policy recommendations

To make dual learning a viable and inclusive pathway in Flanders, several reforms are necessary - targeted both at the system level and at the operational level of schools and employers.

First, the system must become **more flexible to accommodate a wider range of student profiles**. The current focus on ‘strong’ learners risks excluding those who stand to benefit most from work-based learning. Schools and Centres for Part-Time Education (CDOs) should be given greater autonomy to tailor programmes to individual needs, particularly within the onboarding phase. This could involve extended timelines to find a work placement, more varied support pathways, and recognition of progress even if formal dual certification is not achieved.

Second, the administrative and financial burden on schools and employers must be reduced. **Schools that offer both dual and non-dual tracks should receive targeted funding to compensate for the loss of scale economies**. Additional resources should be allocated to support coordinators and mentors. On the employer side, simplifying recognition and insurance procedures - especially for SMEs - would lower entry barriers and expand the pool of available placements.

Third, dual learning in the double finality should be reconsidered. While international examples like Germany showcase success, Flanders lacks the same institutional context. Instead of forcing expansion in the double finality, efforts should concentrate on strengthening dual learning in vocational tracks (BSO), where the match with workplace learning is more evident.

Successful implementation here could later justify gradual expansion.

Fourth, **re-integration routes must be improved**. Students who leave dual learning - due to mismatched expectations or failed placements - currently face high barriers to rejoining full-time education. Schools should be equipped to offer smoother transitions and maintain student engagement through continuous counselling and alternative qualification paths.

Finally, at the European level, **the European Commission can play a strategic role by fostering collaboration and knowledge exchange between Member States**. While models like the German system are often cited, countries with similar institutional structures - such as the Netherlands - offer more realistic lessons for Flanders. The Commission could support peer learning and targeted funding through Erasmus+ and ESF+ for dual learning programmes that prioritise inclusivity, local adaptation, and employer engagement. It should also promote research on context-sensitive models of dual education to avoid one-size-fits-all reforms.

By focusing on flexibility, simplification, and better targeting, Flanders can still turn dual learning into a success story—one that supports all students, not just the few who already fit the mould.

What is BRIDGE ?

BRIDGE is an impact-driven project that aims to build resilient individuals through effective educational transition by formulating robust policy recommendations on education and training policies, the efficient use of public resources and the support of equity and inclusion in education and training systems in the EU.

Further Information:

Verhaest, D. & De Witte, K. (2025). Voorbij de aanloopfase van duaal leren. Leuvense Economische Standpunten 2025/226, p. 12.

**Funded by
the European Union**

BRIDGE is funded by the European Commission in its Horizon Europe framework (grant 101177154). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the granting authority. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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